

EXPANDING ECOTOURISM OPPORTUNITIES: HOW SOLAR ENERGY IS ENABLING, SUSTAINABLE GROWTH FOR SMES IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

Tourism significantly impacts Georgia's economy, particularly in terms of revenue generation and employment opportunities. In 2023, the income generated by the tourism industry surpassed expectations, totaling 4 billion GEL.

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in the sustainable development of the economy. Implementing energy-efficient technologies and transitioning to solar energy reduce operating costs and contribute to the environment's and economy's sustainable development. However, the integration of these technologies, as well as access to financing, is often challenging (Tskiridze, Charaia, 2023; Lashkhi et al., 2022a). Therefore, discussing the main barriers and opportunities SMEs face in financing is important.

SMEs utilizing solar energy technologies not only reduce their carbon emissions but can also enhance their operational efficiency and profitability, thus paving the way for a sustainable tourism industry. This research examines the obstacles and prospects encountered by SMEs looking to secure green financing for solar energy projects in Georgian. Through a combination of literature review, case studies, and empirical analysis, this study examines the current state of solar energy adoption among SMEs in the Georgian ecotourism sector, identifying key drivers, financing challenges, and opportunities. The research employed a qualitative method using a structured questionnaire, with participation from Georgian SMEs representing different regions of Georgia.

Thus, this article aims to discuss the main barriers and opportunities that small and medium-sized enterprises encounter when introducing energy-efficient technologies in the tourism sector, as well as to present the main conclusions and results in this regard.

Keywords: Small and medium enterprises (SMEs), Georgia, financing, green business, tourism, solar energy, sustainable growth.

I. Introduction

Tourism has played a crucial role in the Georgian economy, especially for the last several decades (Gamsakhurdia et al., 2017; Kadagidze et al., 2021). However, in recent years, the concept of ecotourism has spread significantly around the world, with stakeholders becoming more aware of the importance of responsible travel practices for both environmental protection and economic development. Ecotourism has emerged as a promising way to promote harmonization between tourism activities and ecological conservation. In this context, Georgia, with its diverse landscapes and rich cultural heritage, represents a prime opportunity to promote ecotourism initiatives.

Ecotourism is becoming increasingly important in the country's tourism industry and is expanding grows faster than general tourism. Ecotourism is identified as a form of "green tourism" that prioritizes responsible travel practices and aims to preserve vulnerable regions, environments and areas. It emphasizes low-impact travel and sustainable tourism practices, which differentiates it from mass tourism. In addition,

ecotourism is seen as a catalyst for sustainable development, with an emphasis on community involvement and the use of local resources.

The definition of ecotourism emphasizes socially and environmentally responsible travel practices. These practices include non-motorized activities and services that offer the interpretation and experience of nature and culture while maintaining a low environmental impact. It emphasizes the contribution of ecotourism to nature conservation, sustainable use of ecosystems, regional development and improving the quality of life of the local population (GOG, 2020 p., 6-7).

In Georgia, as in the whole world, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play an important role in the sustainable development of the country's economy (Lashkhi et al, 2022b). They account for 67% of employees and about 62% of total value added, which makes their impact on the environment significant.

Small and medium-sized enterprises not only reduce their environmental footprint but also increase their economic viability and sustainability. Moreover, in the face of global challenges such as climate change

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and energy insecurity, Georgia's case is a compelling example of how sustainable tourism practices can contribute to both environmental protection and socio-economic progress. Facing the challenges of a rapidly changing world, the synergy between ecotourism and solar energy represents a promising path for a more resilient and sustainable future for Georgia's tourism industry.

The article discusses the growing landscape of ecotourism in Georgia and investigates the current situation of implementing energy-efficient technologies and renewable energy technologies by MSAs operating in the ecotourism sector and the possibilities for improving activities in this direction.

II. Literature Review

Finding alternative sources of renewable energy is an actively researched area. The extensive utilization of natural resources has undoubtedly resulted in severe environmental consequences, such as air pollution, rising temperatures, damage to forest ecosystems, and desertification in some instances. These interconnected processes have made climate change a pressing issue with significant relevance (Li et al., 2023).

Aligned with the United Nations' vision for a sustainable and diversified global economy with a focus on environmental and societal well-being by 2030 through adhering to safety regulations and minimizing harmful activities (Al-Hababi, 2023), utilizing green and solar energy in particular to achieve sustainable electricity goals becomes particularly crucial (Tvauri, Charaia, 2024). The abundance of sunshine throughout the year offers a unique opportunity for certain countries. Additionally, the UN has implemented significant projects to support the development and implementation of solar panel systems. Installing solar panels on rooftops significantly improves a country's clean energy infrastructure, consequently reducing dependence on fossil fuels. Moreover, with proper management, this approach strengthens the energy system and increases business opportunities for both small and large enterprises. Utilizing sunny days for clean energy generation also presents the potential for export (Banibaqash et al., 2022).

The consumption of solar energy increased by 1%, which is related to the increase in the number of tourists by about 0.35%, highlighting the importance of investments in solar energy in strengthening and supporting the tourism sector. Especially considering factors such as economic stability and a balanced approach to technological advances play an important role in the development of the tourism industry. The implementation of appropriate policies, including increased financing of solar projects, can significantly enhance sustainable energy use initiatives, which in turn will strengthen the tourism sector (J. Li & Cao, 2024).

In other countries, access to financing for the implementation of solar energy technologies by MSAs is characterized by difficulties. Therefore, it is important to discuss the main barriers and opportunities that these enterprises face in financing. In particular: The amount of investment-related costs and required guarantees: these technologies generally require significant preliminary capital investment (Smith et al., 2022), for which

financial institutions require significant own capital as a guarantee, which in most cases is an insurmountable barrier for MSS (Sheikh et al., 2019), despite their long-term savings; Difficulty in the procedure of filling out the credit request: the process of preparing the loan application is long and time-consuming, which prevents the implementation of financing (Dupont, C., & Oberthür, S. 2015). Recent studies also confirm this challenge and emphasize the need to solve the issue; Weaknesses of the relevant policy and legal framework: Incoherent policies, ambiguous regulations, and unstable market conditions create uncertainty (Abashidze, 2023; Taktakishvili, Sachaleli, 2023), which inhibits financial institutions' investment in renewable energy projects for MSS (Brown, C., & Morrad, D. 2020). Stable policy frameworks and clear regulatory guidelines are essential to encouraging private sector investment in sustainable energy projects.

Sources of financing for MSS solar technology projects can be considered, including traditional bank loans. This type of loan is currently one of the main sources, although the qualification criteria were and still remain strict; specialized loan products, green loans, and energy efficiency contracts tailored to the needs of SMEs. These products often provide flexible repayment terms and low interest rates to encourage investment in sustainable energy solutions. Also, innovative financial instruments such as green bonds can mobilize private capital for small and medium-sized enterprises' renewable energy projects (World Bank, 2023).

Government grants and initiatives are a very important resource for financing MSP solar energy projects, as well as providing a modern means of financing MSP: online platforms play a very important role in alternative financing of MSP, mostly with their "relaxed qualification requirements" compared to traditional banks (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2022); "P2P" or emerging sustainability-oriented "peer-to-peer lending" platforms that connect investors directly with borrowers for financing (European Commission, 2024).

III. Research methodology

A mixed-methods approach was used for the research, which includes both qualitative and quantitative research. In order to comprehensively investigate the benefits and challenges of solar energy integration by small and medium-sized ecotourism enterprises in Georgia qualitative analysis is employed to examine different aspects of solar energy implementation in ecotourism. Quantitative methods are utilized to measure the economic and ecological outcomes of solar energy. Within the scope of qualitative research, in-depth interviews were conducted, in which representatives of six hotels located in different regions of Georgia (Radisson Blu Iveria, Orbeliani Residence, Brim Tbilisi, Vazisubani Manor in Gurjaani, Lopota, and Avaliani Brothers Family Hotel in Adjara) participated. To find out the keys to accessing the financing of SMEs, the top managers of the three major banks participating in the green financing program - Bank of Georgia, TBC Bank, and Procreditbank were interviewed.

As part of our quantitative research using a survey method, we interviewed representatives from 40 hotels

across various regions of Georgia (Tbilisi, Adjara, Kakheti, Samegrelo, and Mtskheta-Mtianeti). We strategically selected these diverse regions to gain a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape regarding access to energy-efficient technologies for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) throughout the country. This research aims to identify both the benefits and challenges associated with implementing these technologies and inform future efforts to expand business activities toward sustainable development.

IV. Results

According to the International Energy Agency, between 2019 and 2024, the installed capacity of renewable energy will increase by 50%, in which solar photovoltaics (PV) will play the main role. And according to the International Renewable Energy Agency, by 2050, solar photovoltaic systems will cover the electrical energy needs of a quarter of the world's population, making the sun the second-largest generation source after wind. Asia (50% of the world), North America (20%), and Europe (10%) are leaders in terms of the installation of solar power plants. The socio-economic factor is worth noting: the global solar industry will employ approximately 18 million people by 2050.

Non-governmental organization The Georgian Environmental Outlook investigated the use of energy-efficient technologies in small hotels. The purpose of the study was to determine what information hotel managers and owners have about energy-efficient approaches, how much they use them, and how much they will use energy-efficient technologies in the future. The research was conducted in five municipalities in Georgia - Stepantsminda, Mtskheta, Kobuleti, Khelvachauri, and the city of Batumi - in a total of 26 hotels and was completed in December 2022. It turned out that the main reason for interest in energy-efficient projects in hotels is cost savings. However, some hotels have additional motivations, namely environmental protection or eco-friendly hotel status. Most of the hotel owners have understood how energy-efficient projects can be implemented in their hotels. For example, installing solar PV panels both in Stepantsminda and Kvartsi is an eco-friendly project. Several hotel owners also want to heat their hotels in Stepantsminda with XPS.

In general, the majority of hotel owners are ready to implement energy-efficient projects with co-financing. Hotel owners consider the high cost of projects to be the main problem in implementing energy efficiency projects. As for the low-interest loan for the implementation of energy-efficient projects, the majority of the respondents would not take such a loan. Most of them already have a loan and refrain from taking additional loans. Some of them do not consider this loan to be economically rational. Accordingly, none of the respondents would take an additional loan in this direction. Some of the respondents have heard about the financing of energy-efficient projects. For example, by the Embassy of Japan, UNDP, and GIZ. This information is spread mainly in Stepantsminda municipality and in single cases in Adjara. The research was carried out within the framework of the project "Accelerating the Spread of Green Energy Technologies in the Tourism Sector." This project was implemented by GEO with the financial support of the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Protection, and Nuclear Safety within the framework of GIZ International Climate Initiative small grants.

Based on the research objectives, we conducted an in-depth interview consisting of nine questions. Representatives of six Georgian hotels (Radisson Blu Iveria, Orbeliani Residence, Brim Tbilisi, Vazisubani Manor in Gurjaani, Lopota, and Avaliani Brothers Family Hotel in Adjara) took part in the interview and sent questions via e-mail. These companies use solar panels. Their representatives noted that the goal of switching to green technologies was to save natural resources and increase energy independence. When asked what economic effect they expect from green investments and in what period the payback will take place, the company's representatives noted the reduction of financial costs and the payback in an average of 3-4 years. When asked what recommendations they would give to companies that plan to implement green technologies in the future, company representatives indicated that they should definitely switch because it will help them protect nature, provide financial benefits, and introduce new innovations that will help them expand their business (Table 1).

Table 1. Application of green technologies in Georgian hotel industry

№	The name of the object	Installed power	Annual output	Investment total \$	Payback period
1	Hotel Radisson Blu Iveria	89 kW	125 kW/h	53,500 \$	1-2 years
2	Hotel Orbeliani Residence	35 kW	49,000 kW/h	21,000 \$	3-4 years
3	Brim Hotel Tbilisi	27 kW	40,000 kW/h	16,200 \$	3-4 year
4	Vazisubani estate in Gurjaani	500 kW	630,000 kW/h	279,000 \$	1-2 years
5	Avaliani Brothers Family Hotel (Adjara)	25 kW	33,000 kW/h	28,300 \$	3-4 years
6	Lopota	126.7 kW	160,710 kW/h	77,000 \$	4 years

In terms of quantitative research for identifying both the benefits and challenges associated with implementing energy-efficient technologies and to inform future efforts to expand business activities towards sustainable development, we interviewed representatives from 40 hotels across various regions of Georgia (Tbilisi, Adjara, Kakheti, Samegrelo, and Mtskheta-Mtianeti).

When asked what are the advantages of implementing green technologies in hotels, 68% considered nature protection and ecology, 15% - financial benefits, 8% - energy independence, 7% - saving natural resources, and 2% - others.

Fig 1. Advantages of implementing green technologies in hotels

In a survey of Georgian hotels, 34% faced financial constraints, 31% found the cost of green technologies to be a barrier, 20% lacked sufficient information, 11% considered climatic conditions a challenge, and 4% reported other hindering factors

Fig 2. Factors hindering the use of green technologies in Georgian hotels

When asked whether they plan to expand green technologies in hotels in the future, 52% gave a positive answer, 33% gave a negative answer, and 15% did not have an answer.

Fig 3. Do you plan to expand green technologies in hotels in the future?

To find out the issues of access to financing renewable energy technologies for SMEs, we interviewed the representatives of the largest donor banks, the Bank of Georgia, TBC Bank, and Procredit Bank. Over the last years, the share of green loans in the bank credit portfolio has increased significantly; in 2020, it was 2.2%, in 2021, it was 2.9%, and by the end of 2022, green loans were 3.2% of the entire portfolio. The share of green loans in the total portfolio was on

average 6%, and the highest rate reached about 17 percent.

Thus, by the end of 2022, the total volume of green loans had reached 1.4 billion (US\$ 530 million), which is 3.2% of the total loan portfolio. This was a 15% increase from 2021. However, it is worth noting that the majority of banks were unable to provide data on green loans due to a lack of clarity in reporting standards

As a result of the survey of the respondents, it was determined that the availability of green financing is

limited, which is reflected in the fact that commercial banks themselves do not issue loans. They act as intermediaries and provide funds from international financial institutions for the implementation of solar energy projects in the ecotourism sector. The main large enterprises benefit from these funds, which hinders the development of MSS in the country. In addition, the limited availability of long-term finance for SMEs is noteworthy: banks are reluctant to provide long-term loans for solar energy projects in the ecotourism sector that are perceived as risky.

Banks identified the lack of incentives from state authorities for the introduction of renewable energy as a barrier to financing. Solar energy generation technologies often require larger upfront investments, which can be an insurmountable barrier for small and medium enterprises as well as individuals. Banks refrain from granting such loans and cite the high risk associated with the financing of SMEs as the reason.

Conclusion

The United Nations (UN) adopted 17 sustainable development goals in 2015. He made the fulfillment of these goals the main challenge of humanity and named the year 2030 as the deadline for its fulfillment. By focusing on the concept of energy efficiency, two of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals are met. These are Goal 7 (affordable and clean energy) and Goal 13 (achieving climate sustainability).

Ecotourism, a form of travel focused on protecting and promoting conservation of the natural environment, is an important prerequisite for sustainable economic growth in Georgia. However, the sector faces challenges, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) trying to implement energy-efficient technologies and renewable energy technologies.

The use of solar energy by small and medium-sized enterprises in the Georgian hotel industry expands opportunities for ecotourism and sustainable business development. Although hotels still do not widely use green technologies, everyone agrees that this is the technology of the future, based on the protection of nature, financial benefits, and the introduction of new innovations.

Research has found that investing in solar energy has several advantages. First of all, the use of solar energy significantly reduces costs for representatives of small and medium-sized enterprises. This type of investment is one of those rare investments that implies a guaranteed profit. Finally, self-generated energy increases the energy independence of the customer, which protects him from future rate increases.

Based on the conducted research, several barriers and challenges hindering the widespread adoption of energy efficiency and renewable energy measures among SMEs have been identified. These include a dearth of knowledge and awareness, substantial investment costs coupled with extended payback periods, low energy prices that deter investment in energy efficiency, inadequate monitoring of energy consumption, limited financing options, insufficient understanding of energy-efficient technologies.

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